

D8.1

Project Management Plan

Summary sheet

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Author(s)	Daniela Magalhães (INESC ID), Ana Rita Nunes (INESC ID), Anabel Simões (INESC ID), Hugo Morais (INESC ID)
Contributor(s)	NA
Reviewer(s)	Daniel Herrera (POLIS), Marina Martin Vilches (POLIS), Gergana Dimitrova (F6Stech)
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Disclaimer

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This deliverable Project Management Plan follows the structure used in the Project Management Plans of the following projects, developed under the same Coordination team: Shift2DC and U2Demo.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CINAE	Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D	Deliverable
EC	Distributed Energy Resources
DERs	European Commission
EC	Electric Vehicle Compliant Parking Lot Integrated PV
ePIPVs	Electric Vehicles
EV	Grant Agreement
GA	Innovation Activities
IA	Intellectual Property Rights
IPR	Internal management reports
IMR	Life Cycle Assessment
LCA	Minutes of Meeting
MoM	Milestone

OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PMP	Project Management Plan
PO	Project Officer
PV	Photovoltaic
R	Report
R&D	Research and Development
SC	Scientific Committee
SEN	Sensitive
TG	Target Group
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
V2L	Vehicle-to-Everything
V2X	Vehicle-to-Load
VIPV	Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaic
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable D8.1 - Project Management Plan (PMP) outlines the objectives, scope, governance, execution strategy and monitoring processes to ensure that the SOLAR-MOVE project reaches its main objectives. Overall, the document specifies the SOLAR-MOVE project goals, structure and timeline, while identifying the roles and responsibilities of the consortium partners, the management team, and governance bodies. This deliverable also focuses on key project management processes to track progress effectively, on time and within the budget.

More specifically, the deliverable describes the project's management structure and governance framework, as well as the internal management procedures for coordination, including the project repositories, partner communication channels, and the organisation and types of meetings that will be held during the project. It also establishes procedures to ensure the quality of the project results, from preparation, revision and submission of deliverables, to preparation and submission of reports.

In summary, this deliverable serves as a reference for all SOLAR-MOVE consortium members to consult, supporting effective project implementation and management, and contributing to the achievement of the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement (GA).

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The Project Management Plan (PMP) provides the SOLAR-MOVE consortium with an overview of the project, a clear framework for project governance, roles and responsibilities of the Project Coordination, the Scientific Committee (SC) members, Work Package (WP) and Task Leaders (TL), and General Assembly members. The document also describes the tools and processes needed to achieve the project goals on time.

Additionally, the document also presents preliminary guidance on managing communication and dissemination activities, as well as data management procedures, to support the coordination and successful progress of the project.

1.2 Structure

This document is organised into several sections to guide the reader through the project's structure, management framework, tools, procedures, and quality assurance measures:

Section 1. , Introduction, presents the purpose, objectives, and overall framework of the PMP;

Section 2. , Project Overview, describes briefly the SOLAR-MOVE WPs, including the project Gantt chart, key milestones and planned deliverables;

Section 0, Organisation, Management Structure, and Governance, details the management framework, internal communication channels and the SOLAR-MOVE repositories. It also identifies the project meetings and the procedures for organising them;

Section 4. , Internal Management Procedures, describes the deliverable workflows, from preparation, revision to submission, the preparation of the internal and periodic reports, and the risk management procedures;

Section 5. , Quality Assurance Procedures, identifies the approaches and methodology to ensure high quality standards of the implementation and the project results;

Section 6. , Communication and Dissemination Preliminary Plan, provides guidelines for participation in events, preparation of scientific articles and release of public outreach materials;

Section 7. , Evidence and Record-keeping, an overview of documents that partners must have during and after the project is finalised;

Section 8. , Conclusions, gives an overview of the document.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

The PMP defines the processes and quality guidelines needed to align the project's tasks and deliverables, facilitating an effective progress of the project. This PMP provides an overarching guidance for all project tasks and deliverables, and it is directly connected to the following deliverables:

D8.2 – Project Management Plan update: D8.2 updates the coordination and management procedures adopted in D8.1.

D7.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan and **D7.2 – Update Dissemination and Communication plan:** D7.1 covers the SOLAR-MOVE dissemination and communication plan and respective update at M24 (D7.2).

D8.3 – Data Management Plan; D8.4 – Data Management plan update M24; D8.5 – Data Management plan update M42: D8.3 outlines the SOLAR-MOVE Data Management guidelines to be followed by the consortium, in compliance with FAIR principles and aligned with EC policies. It is followed by respective updates at M24 (D8.4) and at M42 (D8.5)

2. Project Overview

This section defines the objectives (Section 2.1), presents the consortium (Section 2.2), Work Packages (Section 2.3), timeline, milestones and deliverables (Section 0), and innovations and solutions (Section 0) of the SOLAR-MOVE project.

2.1 Project summary and objectives

The SOLAR-MOVE project was funded under the call *HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-05: PV-integrated electric mobility applications*, within the Horizon Europe – Innovation Actions (IA) program. This call targeted advances in photovoltaic (PV) power generation to support a clean energy system and achieve net-zero emissions. The main expected outcomes of this call were to open new market opportunities for Vehicle-Integrated PV (VIPV) in road transport, to reduce usage of the electricity grid and increase the range of Electric Vehicles (EV), and to contribute to making road transport cost and energy-efficient and climate-neutral.

Within this context, the SOLAR-MOVE project aims to contribute to the massive adoption of EVs, minimising their impact on the power grid. Different solutions are being proposed for different VIPV ecosystems: in cities, in residential and service buildings, in passenger transportation and on highways, along with the development of five Electric Vehicle Compliant Parking Lot Integrated PV (ePIPVs), each with different characteristics.

The specific aims of the project are to:

- Reduce the regulatory barriers to the development of VIPV strategies;
- Propose innovative PV solutions including the encapsulation process;
- Propose viable VIPV vehicles;
- Demonstrate VIPV and ePIPV solutions;
- Propose Business models enabling VIPV solutions;

- Design grid-friendly eIPVs;
- Propose solutions to optimise the operation of eIPVs;
- Increase the participation of eIPVs in grid services;
- Contribute to the increase of interoperability of VIPV and eIPVs;
- Improve the current Use Cases repository of Bridge;
- Increase the use of renewables and other Distributed Energy Resources (DERs).

In order to achieve the objectives, the consortium (comprised of 34 partners across 16 countries) will develop innovative VIPV solutions, including *i)* tools to be integrated in VIPV; *ii)* VIPV prototypes (Heavy-duty vehicles with PV in the trailer, garbage trucks, passenger buses, last-mile delivery and motorhome); *iii)* VIPV Use Optimisation solutions to maximise the range of the VIPVs; and *iv)* eIPV for diverse applications (in highways, opportunity charging for eBus, eIPVs at municipality level, public eIPV in commercial areas and private eIPVs).

These solutions will be demonstrated in six pilots across six countries (Denmark, Greece, Turkey, Portugal, Albania, and Slovenia). The findings will contribute to the elaboration of policy recommendations to support the adoption of VIPV and eIPV, guidelines for municipalities to simplify the regulatory frameworks and the procurement process for VIPS and eIPVs solutions, and incentives to facilitate the mass deployment of these technologies.

2.2 SOLAR-MOVE Consortium

The SOLAR-MOVE Consortium comprises 35 beneficiary partners, four associated partners and one affiliated entity, from sixteen European countries (Portugal, Sweden, Denmark, Albania, Turkey, United Kingdom, Greece, Luxembourg, Germany, Belgium, Spain, Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, New Zealand, France). Their expertise and roles in the project are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - SOLAR-MOVE consortium expertise and role in the project

Entity	Short Name / Logo	Beneficiary type	Description	Expertise	Role in SOLAR-MOVE
INESC ID - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM LISBOA	<p>INESC ID</p>	Beneficiary	R&D Institute	Development of ePIPV Optimal Operation Tools.	<p>Coordination/Academic solution provider.</p> <p>Coordination of WP8.</p> <p>Responsible for ePIPV planning and design tools & Hardware ePIPV support.</p> <p>Leader PT and NZ pilots.</p>
CNET CENTRE FOR NEW ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES SA	<p>EDP NEW</p>	Beneficiary	R&D Company	Provision of flexibility services to system operators. Conclusion of validation of the pilots.	Coordination of WP5 and MS6.
INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIENCIA	<p>INESC TEC</p>	Beneficiary	R&D Institute	<p>Development/implementation of solvers and optimisation algorithms.</p> <p>Assessment of flexibility opportunities.</p>	Development of the intelligent support tools enabling flexibility.

CLEAN MOTION AB	CleanM 	Beneficiary	Car OEM	Development of encapsulation technologies. Evaluation of the impact of improvements on the PV system and search for new business opportunities. Vehicle manufacturer.	Participation in PT pilot.
DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU 	Beneficiary	University	Development/implementation of solvers and optimisation algorithms.	Coordination of WP3. Participation in DK pilot. Responsible for the system integration and flexibility services adapted to ePIPVs in WP1.
MOBICOM PRO APS	Mobicom 	Beneficiary	Tech & Software	Development and integration of algorithms in platforms and ePIPV Optimal Operation Tools.	Participation in DK pilot.
UNIVERSITETI POLITEKNIK I TIRANES	UPT 	Beneficiary	University	Universiteti politeknik i tiranes	Participation in AL Pilot.

Qendra Sustainability and Innovation Albania SUSALB	SUSALB 	Beneficiary	R&D Company	Development of ePIPV Optimal Operation Tools.	Leader of AL pilots in WP5.
BASHKIA TIRANE	TiranaM 	Beneficiary	Municipality	Municipal and governmental collaboration: Fleet of EVs	Participation in AL Pilot.
Operatori i Shperndarjes se Energjise Elektrike GROUP	OSHEE 	Beneficiary	Energy suppliers	Operation of grids. Fleet of EVs	Participation in AL Pilot.

BOZANKAYA RAYLI SISTEMLER A.S.	<p>Bozankaya</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>Car OEM</p>	<p>Identification of the needs in the solar panel electric bus sector and following up on tenders. Vehicle manufacturer.</p>	<p>Coordination of WP4. Leader of TK pilot. Responsible for cells, modules and electronics integration of VIPVs.</p>
MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	<p>METU</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>University</p>	<p>Development/implementation of solvers and optimisation algorithms. Commissioning of solutions to be tested in pilots.</p>	<p>Leader of TK Pilot in WP5.</p>
ODTU GUNES ENERJISI UYGULAMA VE ARA STIRMA MERKEZI	<p>GUNAM</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>R&D Company</p>	<p>Development of encapsulation technologies.</p>	<p>Participation in TK pilot. Responsible for module design for different types of VIPVs.</p>

<p>ILERI ARGE TEKNOLOJILERI MUHENDISLIK YAZILIM EGITIM DANISMANLIJK SANAYI VE TICARET LIMITED SIRKETI</p>	<p>iTech</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>R&D Company</p>	<p>Development of encapsulation technologies.</p>	<p>Coordination of WP2 and MS2. Participation in TK pilot.</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE</p>	<p>Strath</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>University</p>	<p>Dissemination activities</p>	<p>Participation in TK pilot.</p>
<p>ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION</p>	<p>NTUA</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>University</p>	<p>Development of ePIPV Optimal Operation Tools</p>	<p>Coordination of WP3. Participation in GR pilot.</p>
<p>VIOMICHANIA EIDIKON KATASKEVON A. KAOUSIS ANONYMOS ETAIREIA</p>	<p>Kaoussis</p>	<p>Beneficiary</p>	<p>Car OEM</p>	<p>Vehicle manufacturer.</p>	<p>Leader of Greek Pilot. Participation in DK pilot.</p>

LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST 	Beneficiary	R&D Company	Development of ePIPV Optimal Operation Tools	Participation in TK, PT and NZ pilots.
SONO MOTORS GMBH	SonoM 	Beneficiary	R&D Company	Planning and Operation tools for ePIPVs. Development of encapsulation technologies.	Coordination of MS3. Participation in DK, TK, SI and GR pilots.
POLIS	POLIS 	Beneficiary	Policies and regulation	Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Policy and regulation guidelines.	Coordination of WP7.
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA EN ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	IREC 	Beneficiary	R&D company	Development and integration of advanced energy-materials.	Leader of task 6.1.

F6S EU TECH INNOVATION NETWORK DESIGNATED ACTIVITY COMPANY	F6Stech 	Beneficiary	Company	Development of innovation support tools and methodologies for business model evaluation.	Coordination of WP6.
COMSENSUS, KOMUNIKACIJE IN SENZORIKA, DOO	ComS 	Beneficiary	Tech & Software	Development and integration of algorithms in platforms.	Participation in GR and SI pilots.
DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS	DAEM 	Beneficiary	Municipality	Municipal and governmental collaboration.	Leader of task 5.3.
EMOTION SRL	EMOT 	Beneficiary	Tech & Software	Development and integration of smart-charging infrastructure.	Participation in SI pilot.

ADRIA MOBIL PROIZVODNJA, TRGOVINA IN STORITVE NOVO MESTO DOO	ADRIA 	Beneficiary	Car OEMs	Vehicle manufacturer.	Leader of SI Pilot.
UNIVERSITY OF CANTERBURY	UCant 	Beneficiary	University	Advanced solar applications and sustainable energy research	Participation in PT and NZ pilots.
MC SHARED SERVICES SA	SONAE 	Beneficiary	Retailer	Provider of fleet management solutions.	Participation in PT and NZ pilots.

ELERGONE ENERGIA, LDA	<p style="text-align: center;">ELER</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Affiliated</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Renewables & Environment</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Coordinating and optimizing the energy utilization and efficiency across the entire retail operation.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Participation in PT and NZ pilots. Responsible for providing technical expertise and operational oversight for energy-infrastructure management, consumption monitoring, and sustainability and cost-efficiency improvements.</p>
AIGLON ANONYMI VIOMICHANIKI KAI EMPORIKI ETAIREIA AYTOKINITON	<p style="text-align: center;">Citroen</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Beneficiary</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">R&D Company</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Development of encapsulation technologies. Vehicle manufacturer.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Participation in GR pilot.</p>
Alex Andersen. Ølund A/S	<p style="text-align: center;">AA</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Beneficiary</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Company</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Integration of sustainable logistics operations, including cold-chain transport and solar-equipped terminals</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Leader of DK pilots.</p>

Boost Urban Thrills, S.A	<p>BOOST</p>	<p>Associated</p>	<p>Company</p>	<p>Management of electric and sustainable tour fleets and provision of logistics solutions.</p>	<p>Participation in PT pilot, using a VIPV in their regular distribution activities.</p>
BARRAQUEIRO TRANSPORTES, S.A.	<p>Barr</p>	<p>Associated</p>	<p>Company</p>	<p>Operation of comprehensive public-transport networks, ensuring connectivity across urban, peri-urban and rural areas.</p>	<p>Provide information allowing the evaluation of the impact of VIPV solutions on passenger buses.</p>
OPERATORI SISTEMITE TRANSMETIMITOST - SHOQERI ANONIME	<p>OST</p>	<p>Associated</p>	<p>Company</p>	<p>Operation and development of the national transmission grid.</p>	<p>Provision of grid and operational data for flexibility service assessments, notably Transmission System Operator operating needs.</p>
WATT & WELL	<p>W&W</p>	<p>Associated</p>	<p>R&D Company</p>	<p>E-mobility electronics supplier, with essential subsystems for DC charging stations.</p>	<p>Provision of hardware for the development of DC/DC V2G stations.</p>

AL, Albania; DC, Direct Current; DK, Denmark; ePIPVs: Electric Vehicle Compliant Parking Lot Integrated PV; GR, Greece; MS, Milestone; NZ, New Zealand; PT, Portugal; R&D, Research and Development; SI, Sweden; TK, Turkey; V2G, Vehicle-to-grid; VIPV, Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaics; WP, Work Package.

2.3 Work Structure

The SOLAR-MOVE project is organised into eight WPs, divided into four phases:

- i) Foundations (WP1);
- ii) Solutions (WP2 and WP3);
- iii) Demonstration (WP4 and WP5);
- iv) Business Strategies and Policies (WP6 and WP7).

The first four months of the project will be devoted to the analysis of the existing regulatory frameworks in EU countries (WP1). The following 18 months will focus on R&I development under WP2 (development of VIPV solutions) and WP3 (development of software and hardware solutions for ePIPVs). WP4 (VIPVs Demonstration) and WP5 (ePIPVs Demonstration) will start in month M13 with the specification and organisation of the deployment of the pilots. WP6 is planned to start in Month M16 and will focus on tasks related to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), exploitation and business-related activities. WP7 (Dissemination and Standardisation) and WP8 (Project Management) will support the overall implementation during the whole project life cycle. The SOLAR-MOVE WPs and their connections are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Work Packages Organisation

WP descriptions and respective beneficiary leaders are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - SOLAR-MOVE Work Package (WP) details

WP	WP name	WP description	Leader
1	Regulation, Services and Use Cases	Lay the groundwork for the SOLAR-MOVE solutions and pilots, by identifying key regulatory barriers, mapping flexibility services, defining business and system use case centered on the pilots and implementing the architecture of the Information and Communication Technology infrastructure.	<u>NTUA</u>
2	VIPVs Innovation and Development	Develop and integrate advanced solar technologies for VIPV by designing and fabricating solar modules with higher efficiency, performance, and durability and by developing power electronic devices allowing for a more efficient integration of PV in the VIPVs system.	<u>iTech</u>
3	Planning and Operation of eIPVs	Develop software solutions for eIPVs to estimate PV production from VIPVs and eIPVs, develop tools allowing the participation in flexibility services and the planning, design and management of eIPVs. Advance the design of hardware solutions. Evaluate the broader impact of VIPVs and eIPVs in the European power system.	<u>DTU</u>
4	VIPVs Demonstration	Demonstrate several VIPV solutions that will undergo several activities to make sure the pilots and tests run without issues.	<u>Bozankaya</u>
5	eIPVs in cities and building	Demonstrate several eIPVs solutions that will undergo several activities to make sure the pilots and tests run without issues.	<u>EDP NEW</u>
6	Business Models and Funding Opportunities	Create new business opportunities. Develop all tasks related to LCA, CBA, exploitation and business-related activities.	<u>F6STech</u>
7	Dissemination and Standardisation	Promote project visibility through communication and dissemination strategies, knowledge transfer, and connections with national and European initiatives. Participate and support standardisation entities by publishing policy recommendations and guidelines.	<u>POLIS</u>

8	Project Management	Guarantee project execution and alignment with objectives, budget, and timeline while maintaining technical and scientific excellence. Adhere to open data policies, commercialisation, intellectual property rights (IPR), and risk management to ensure project success.	<u>INESC ID</u>
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2.4 Timeline, Milestones and Deliverables

The SOLAR-MOVE project has a duration of 42 months, starting on the 1st of November 2025, and finishing by the end of April 2029. Figure 2 illustrates the timeline of the project, with the start date and duration of the project tasks (in blue bars) and WPs (purple bars). Figure 2 also shows the seven progress milestones (blue circles, also identified in Table 3), the two periodic EC/CINEA reporting reviews (light blue triangles) and the annual in-person General Assemblies (yellow triangles, also identified in Table 8)

 Consortium Meetings
 External Project Reviews
 Milestones

Figure 2 - SOLAR-MOVE Gantt Chart

Table 3 defines the seven progress milestones of the SOLAR-MOVE project (blue circles in Figure 2).

Table 3 - SOLAR-MOVE list of milestones

Milestone No	Milestone Name	WP	Means of Verification	Due Date
1	Detailed definition of UCs to be considered in the development of SOLARMOVE solutions and pilots	1	Delivery of the definition of the use cases providing the first vision of the interactions, algorithms and information exchange needs between stakeholders (D1.3 and D1.4).	M12
2	Prototypes of VIPV solutions (Cells, encapsulation, MPPTs)	2	The general description of the prototypes will be included in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3.	M22
3	Prototypes of VIPV vehicles to be tested in Pilots	2	The five VIPV solutions that will be tested in SOLARMOVE will be delivered to demonstration (WP4).	M24
4	Planning and Operation tools for ePIPVs	3	The ePIPVs will be tested in five pilots that will be developed in WP5 (D3.3).	M24
5	Commissioning of the SOLARMOVE solutions to be tested in the pilots	4, 5	Specification of pilots, implementation, and simulation results will be described in deliverables D4.1, D4.2, D5.1 and D5.2.	M27
6	Conclusion of the validation phase of the pilots	4, 5	Validation of UCs and KPIs tested in the pilots. This MS enables the definition of roadmaps, guidelines and business strategies (D4.4 and D5.4).	M39
7	Exploitation Methodology	6	Delivery of an internal document to be shared with partners via project repository to align tasks and responsibilities throughout the project.	M19

Table 4 identifies the forty-three SOLAR-MOVE project deliverables, highlighting the respective leaders, dissemination level, type of document, and due date.

Dissemination level:

- Nine deliverables will contain sensitive information (dissemination level, SEN): information on the deployment activities performed in the different pilots (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, D5.1, D5.2, D5.3); the exploitation methodology of the solutions developed (D6.5), and two internal progress reports of the activities (D8.6 and D8.7). Due to their sensitive content, these deliverables will be available only to the SOLAR-MOVE consortium and the European Commission (EC);
- Thirty-four deliverables will be public and available on the project website and the CORDIS website;

Type of document:

- Thirty-seven deliverables will have the format of a report (R);
- Six deliverables will have OTHER formats: repository for use cases (Deliverable D1.3), a specification and design of PV solutions (Deliverables D2.1, D2.2), a set of advanced algorithms and the prototyping of the integration between trailers and trucks (Deliverable D2.3), the prototype of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) / Vehicle-to-Load (V2L) solution (Deliverable D2.4) and the integration of PVs (Deliverable D2.5). OTHER deliverables will always be complemented by short reports describing the solution/repository/algorithms to be submitted in the EC portal.

Table 4 - SOLAR-MOVE list of deliverables

Deliverable	Deliverable Name	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date
D1.1	Regulatory Framework Mapping	1	POLIS	R	PU	M09
D1.2	Flexibility Services Mapping	1	DTU	R	PU	M11
D1.3	Use Case Repository	1	NTUA	OTHER	PU	M12
D1.4	Cybersecurity and Interoperability	1	ComS	R	PU	M12
D2.1	TOPCon and SHJ Cells Prototypes	2	iTech	OTHER	PU	M20

D2.2	PV Modules adapted to VIPVs	2	iTech	OTHER	PU	M21
D2.3	MPPT Including New Algorithms	2	SonoM	OTHER	PU	M22
D2.4	V2L and V2G for VIPV Prototype	2	ComS	OTHER	PU	M22
D2.5	VIPVs Prototypes	2	Bozankaya	OTHER	PU	M24
D2.6	Fleet Management Optimisation	2	NTUA	R	PU	M24
D2.7	PV Devices Performance Certification	2	iTech	R	PU	M26
D3.1	PV Production in VIPVs Estimation	3	LIST	R	PU	M18
D3.2	Flexibility Assessment	3	INESC TEC	R	PU	M19
D3.3	ePIPVs Planning	3	INESC ID	R	PU	M20
D3.4	ePIPVs Management and Operation	3	DTU	R	PU	M21
D3.5	ePIPV Hardware Solutions	3	INESC ID	R	PU	M24
D3.6	Impact of ePIPV in Energy and Power Systems	3	DTU	R	PU	M26
D4.1	VIPVs Detailed Specification of VIPVs pilots	4	Bozankaya	R	SEN	M18
D4.2	VIPVs Pilots Installation and Commissioning	4	AA	R	SEN	M24
D4.3	VIPVs Pilots Monitoring and Assessment	4	Kaoussis	R	SEN	M33
D4.4	VIPVs Lessons Learned in Pilots	4	Bozankaya	R	PU	M39
D5.1	ePIPVs Detailed Specification of Pilots	5	EDP NEW	R	SEN	M18
D5.2	ePIPVs Pilots Installation and Commissioning	5	SUSALB	R	SEN	M24

D5.3	ePIPVs Pilots Monitoring and Assessment	5	NTUA	R	SEN	M33
D5.4	ePIPVs Lessons Learned in the Pilots	5	EDP NEW	R	PU	M39
D6.1	LCA of VIPV Technologies	6	IREC	R	PU	M39
D6.2	CBA of VIPV Technologies	6	LIST	R	PU	M40
D6.3	Business Strategies and Funding Opportunities	6	F6STech	R	PU	M30
D6.4	Business Strategies and Funding Opportunities Update M42	6	F6STech	R	PU	M42
D6.5	Exploitation Methodology	6	F6STech	R	SEN	M19
D7.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	7	POLIS	R	PU	M06
D7.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan Update M24	7	POLIS	R	PU	M24
D7.3	Strategy for Standardization	7	SonoM	R	PU	M15
D7.4	Policies and Recommendations for Procurement	7	POLIS	R	PU	M36
D7.5	Regulations and Incentives Policies	7	POLIS	R	PU	M39
D7.6	Guidelines for VIPV and ePIPV Development	7	INESC ID	R	PU	M42
D8.1	Project Management Plan	8	INESC ID	R	PU	M02
D8.2	Project Management Plan Update	8	INESC ID	R	PU	M18
D8.3	Data Management Plan	8	INESC ID	R	PU	M06
D8.4	Data Management Plan Update M24	8	INESC ID	R	PU	M24

D8.5	Data Management Plan Update M42	8	INESC ID	R	PU	M42
D8.6	Intermediate progress report M15	8	INESC ID	R	SEN	M15
D8.7	Intermediate progress report M36	8	INESC ID	R	SEN	M36

2.5 Innovation and solutions

The SOLAR-MOVE project aims to develop several solutions that will impact the cost and barriers of the VIPV and ePIPV, increase global efficiency of VIPVs, assess the impact of VIPVs in different usages, define business strategies adapted to VIPVs and ePIPVs, participate in flexibility services increasing incomes and in the development of new Distributed Energy Resources, Demand Response and distributed flexibility programs.

A total of 20 solutions have been proposed, ranging from hardware prototypes to software solutions (Figure 3). One of the goals of the project is to bring those solutions close to the market (high Technology Readiness Level).

Figure 3 – SOLAR-MOVE Solutions

3. Organisation, Management Structure, and Governance

The achievement of the SOLAR-MOVE project's goals and outputs (deliverables, milestones, solutions) mentioned in the previous section depends on the coordinated engagement and expertise of all consortium partners and the participation of external stakeholders. To support this collaboration, the project is driven by an effective management framework designed to facilitate decision-making, oversee day-to-day implementation, and maintain structured communication with the EC. This framework ensures alignment across partners and supports the efficient and timely delivery of the work plan.

The project's management strategy combines top-down guidance, provided through its formal governance bodies, with bottom-up contributions stemming from the active involvement of task and work package teams. This dual approach encourages responsive problem-solving, knowledge exchange, and reiterative project development.

The SOLAR-MOVE governance model is organised mainly into four complementary layers (see Figure 4 , each with clearly defined roles and responsibilities:

- **Project Coordinator** – responsible for administrative, contractual and financial oversight, and the main interface with the EC (Section 3.1);
- **General Assembly** – the project's highest decision-making body, guiding strategic direction and ensuring coherence with the project's vision and Grant Agreement (GA) (Section 3.2);
- **Scientific Committee** – ensures scientific and methodological consistency across work packages, monitors technical progress, and supports risk mitigation (Section 3.3);
- **Advisory Board** - an independent entity that offers external expertise and strategic direction to assure the scientific and practical applicability of project outcomes (Section 3.4).

Furthermore, additional key roles will support the Coordination Team, such as the WP leader, TL, Legal officer and Data protection officer, whose responsibilities are described in Section 3.5 .

Further details on each governance and management structure will be provided in the following sections.

Figure 4 - SOLAR-MOVE management structure and governance

3.1 Project Coordinator

Role: ensure the seamless execution of all project components, including operations, administration, and scientific activities. INESC ID is responsible for overseeing the entire SOLAR-MOVE project and has established a Project Coordination Team (Table 5).

Composition of the Project Coordination Team: Project Coordinator, Project Manager and Financial Manager, all from INESC ID, a Communication Manager from POLIS and an Innovation Manager from F6S. Furthermore, the team also includes a Communication Officer from INESC ID to support the alignment between INESC ID and POLIS.

Table 5 - SOLAR-MOVE Project Coordination Team and their roles

Role	Institution	Name	Function
Project Coordinator (PC)	INESC ID	Hugo Morais	Primary representative and responsible of the SOLAR-MOVE project, and intermediary between Parties and the Granting Authority. Responsible for overall coordination of the project execution, assisted in his role and responsibilities by the Project Manager.
Project Manager	INESC ID	Daniela Magalhães; Anabel Simões; Ana Rita Nunes	Responsible for overseeing the administrative and financial management of the project, supporting the Project Coordinator by ensuring that the project outputs meet the highest standards and are completed on time. Communicates with the European Commission, consortium, advisory board and stakeholders.
Financial Manager	INESC ID	Ilda Ribeiro	Manages all financial aspects of the project
Communication Manager	POLIS	Marina Vilches (Mariana Carmo – Communication Officer)	Responsible for planning and execution of dissemination and communication activities, ensures consistent projects branding, and promotes engagement with the target audience.
Innovation Manager	F6S	Gergana Dimitrova	Leads the innovation and exploitation strategy, ensuring alignment between research objectives, results' exploitation, and user validation. Defines Innovation KPIs and consolidates partners' exploitation plans.

Section 6.4.2 of the SOLAR-MOVE Consortium Agreement (CA) delineates the responsibilities of the Project Coordinator and the Coordination Team. These responsibilities encompass a broad spectrum of contractual, managerial, and supervisory duties, as outlined in Table 6.

Table 6 - SOLAR-MOVE Coordination team role

SOLAR-MOVE Coordination Team responsibilities	
Oversight and Compliance	Monitoring the progress of all project activities to ensure that all partners adhere to the regulations outlined in both the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the GA.
Communication within the consortium	Maintaining current contact lists, facilitating effective communication among partners, and ensuring the prompt sharing of pertinent project information to support efficient internal communication.
Managing reports and documentation	Gathering and verifying technical and financial information from partners to ensure accuracy and consistency before submission to the Granting Authority, along with any other required documents.
Organization and Conducting meetings	Preparing for and conducting General Assembly meetings, developing agendas, facilitating sessions, recording and distributing minutes, proposing decisions when appropriate, and monitoring the implementation of agreed-upon actions.
Information Flow within the Consortium	Ensuring that all Parties receive the necessary documents and information required to perform their roles in the project effectively.
Financial Management	This encompasses the administration of EU fund disbursements in accordance with the GA and CA, along with all related financial oversight procedures and reporting responsibilities.
Providing Official Documents	Supplying partners with official copies or originals of documents exclusively held by the Coordinator upon request, when such documents are required for claims, justification, or other legitimate purposes.
Coordinating Modifications	Assuming responsibility for creating and submitting any amendments to the GA following their official approval by the General Assembly.

3.2 General Assembly

Role: the primary decision-making entity of the consortium. In this assembly, key strategic decisions are made that may influence the execution and overall success of the project.

Composition of the General Assembly: Project Coordination Team (Project Coordinator/Project Manager) that oversees the General Assembly, and a single representative from the beneficiaries (see Table 7 for the list of partners’ representatives, which may alter throughout the project).

Each entity is entitled to cast a single vote. If the beneficiary representative is unavailable, they may designate a substitute or a proxy. They may also extend invitations to additional beneficiary members,

but only one member of the entity will have the right to vote. According to the CA, each member of the General Assembly possesses the right to discuss, negotiate, and make decisions on all matters.

Table 7 - SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly representatives

Number	Partner	Representant
1	INESC ID	Hugo Morais (Chairperson)
2	EDP NEW	Motaz Ayiad
3	INESC TEC	António Faria
4	Clean Motion AB	William Collings
5	DTU	Peter Bach Andersen
6	MOBICOM	Christian Nordling
7	UPT	Alfred Pjetri
8	SUSALB	Bajram Ilazi
9	Tirana M	Lek Hakani
10	OSHEE	Silvana Xheka
11	Bozankaya	Batuhan Yildiz
12	METU	Murat Gol
13	GUNAM	Rasit Turan
14	iTechSolar	Gokhan Aslan
15	Uni. Of Strathclyde	Safak Bayram
16	NTUA	Elissaios Sarmas
17	Kaoussis	Antonios Kaousis
18	LIST	Ulrich Leopold

19	SonoM	Ariel Avila
20	POLIS	Daniel Herrera
21	IREC	Josh Eichman
22	F6STech	Gergana Dimitrova
23	ComS	Miha Smolnikar
24	DAEM	Ilia Christantoni
25	EMOT	Edoardo Mancinelli
26	ADRIA	Tomaz Tomazic
27	Ucant	Hamish Avery
28	SONAE	Catarina Soares
29	Citroen	Nikos Kasimatis
35	Alex Andersen	Jan Andersen

Once per year, the General Assembly convenes in person, resulting in a total of five meetings throughout the duration of the project. Moreover, it was decided during the Kick-off Meeting to hold an additional virtual General Assembly meeting during mid-project year. More details about the General Assembly meetings are provided in Section 4.3.1.

The procedures and responsibilities of the General Assembly are specified in Section 6.3 of the SOLAR-MOVE CA [1] and are detailed in Table 8.

Table 8 - SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly

SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly Procedures	
Financial governance	The General Assembly can authorise modifications to the consortium’s financial plan, including the reallocation of the EU contribution among beneficiaries when duly justified.
Amendments to the GA	The General Assembly may suggest revisions to Annex 1 (Description of Action) and Annex 2 (Estimated Budget). Any proposed amendment shall thereafter be submitted to the Granting Authority for approval.
Background management	The General Assembly is authorised to suggest updates, modifications, or withdraw the Background in attachment 1.

Consortium Composition	The General Assembly may propose the inclusion of a new beneficiary to the project or recommend the removal of an existing beneficiary when justified.
Project Coordination Agreement Changes	The General Assembly might request substantial project governance or contractual modifications from the Granting Authority. These include hiring a new Project Coordinator, suspending the project, or cancelling the Grant and Consortium Agreements.
Management of Breaches and Defaults	The General Assembly can evaluate if a partner is in breach of the Consortium or GA. If non-compliance is found, the General Assembly may identify the partner as a defaulter, suspend its consortium membership, and take legal or litigation action.
Decision-Making Procedures	General Assembly decisions can be made in person or by email consultation. A simple majority of (2/3) of votes is needed to approve. A beneficiary can veto a decision that it deems as potentially harmful.

3.3 Scientific Committee

Role: The Scientific Committee meets once a month to discuss project management topics, assess risk management and the progress of the technical work.

Composition of the Scientific Committee: Project Coordination Team (chaired by the Project Manager), and the WP leaders (Table 9).

Table 9 - SOLAR-MOVE Scientific Committee members

Role	Institution	Representant
Project Coordinator	INESC ID	Hugo Morais
Project Manager	INESC ID	Daniela Magalhães Anabel Simões Ana Rita Nunes
WP1 Leader	NTUA	Elissaios Sarmas
WP2 Leader	iTech	Gokhan Aslan
WP3 Leader	DTU	Peter Andersen
WP4 Leader	Bozankaya	Batuhan Yildiz
WP5 Leader	EDP NEW	Motaz Ayiad
WP6 Leader	FS6	Gergana Dimitrova

WP7 Leader	POLIS	Daniel Herrera Marina Martin Vilches
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The main SC roles are presented in Table 10.

Table 10 - SOLAR-MOVE Scientific Committee roles

SOLAR-MOVE Scientific Committee roles	
Implementation of GA decisions	Ensure that all strategic and technical decisions of the General Assembly are implemented.
Project Compliance and Monitoring	Monitor the implementation of project activities to confirm compliance with the GA, and propose alterations to the GA to the General Assembly.
Quality Assurance of Scientific Outputs	Monitor the project's technical and scientific progress to ensure excellence in methodology, results, and outputs.
Risk Identification and Mitigation	Identify scientific, technological, and implementation risks, and suggest mitigation for the risks.
Coordination and Information Flow	Facilitate the flow of information across tasks of each WP and between WPs.
Tracking Milestones and Deliverables	Monitor milestones and deliverables to ensure timely completion and early detection of deviations.
Support to the Coordinator	Assist the Project Coordinator to prepare for European Commission reporting and review meetings.

3.4 SOLAR-MOVE Advisory Board Forum

Role: the advisory board forum will provide insightful perspectives on the project, provide valuable feedback on SOLAR-MOVE's methodologies, solutions and innovations, discuss policy regulations, and align the project with market expectations to boost the exploitation potential of SOLAR-MOVE results.

Composition of the Advisory Board Forum: broad range of stakeholders, including PV cell manufacturers and integrators; vehicle, battery and electronic equipment manufacturers, fleet operators, car Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), the energy sector (system operators, energy producers, energy retailers and aggregators, energy service companies), research institutions and academia (scientific community, R&D, program projects), technology providers (such as software companies, hardware, IoT service providers, building operators, weather services and cybersecurity solution providers), standardisation bodies and policymakers, public authorities and regulators. Key recognised members of this stakeholder ecosystem will be invited to join webinars organised by the project, with the capacity of the Advisory Board.

Structure of the Advisory Board Forum webinars: the webinars are planned to start at M9, and will take place every six months, each focusing on a specific topic, ranging from Regulations and Policies, to VIPV Innovation and Development, Planning and operation of the eIPVs, VIPVs and eIPVs demonstration and lessons learned. Prior to each webinar, the Advisory Board stakeholders will have access to relevant materials/reports from the project. They will have the opportunity to discuss their perspectives during the webinar and afterwards will be asked to provide feedback on project progress.

The main responsibilities of this Advisory Board are listed in Table 11.

Table 11 - SOLAR-MOVE Advisory Board Responsibilities

SOLAR-MOVE Advisory Board	
Engagement in SOLAR-MOVE Webinars	Attend project webinars and provide informed feedback, recommendations, and perspectives on the project's progress and emerging results.
Support finding opportunities and strategic initiatives	Identify opportunities, channels, and strategies that promote the replication, adoption, and implementation of SOLAR-MOVE solutions in practical applications.
Innovation and Feasibility Assessment	Provide expert assessments of the innovation, utility, and market potential of the SOLAR-MOVE technologies and methodologies.
Participation in General Assembly Discussion	Participate in the SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly meetings, if considered necessary by the consortium, taking part in discussions and contributing to the decision-making process. Members of the Advisory Board shall not have the right to vote.

3.5 Other roles supporting the Coordination

Other key players will contribute to the SOLAR-MOVE developments: Work Package (WP) Leader (Section 3.5.1), Task Leader (Section 3.5.2), Legal officer (Section 3.5.3) and Data protection officer (Section 3.5.4).

3.5.1 Work Package Leader

Role: the WP Leader plays a key role in ensuring that all activities and tasks of a certain work package are delivered on time, within scope and according to high-quality standards.

WP leader identification: SOLAR-MOVE project is structured into eight WPs, each led by a designated beneficiary (Table 2). In general, each WP consists of four to seven tasks, with some WPs running for a shorter duration (12 months), while others spanning the entire duration of the project (42 months). The SOLAR-MOVE WP leaders have been identified in Table 9.

The main activities and responsibilities of the WP leaders in the SOLAR-MOVE project are listed in Table 12.

Table 12 - WP Leader roles

SOLAR-MOVE WP Leader roles	
Coordination of WP Activities	Organise and manage all WP tasks to meet objectives and deliverables.
Facilitation of Information Flow	Ensure clear and efficient communication across WP tasks and maintain collaboration with other WPs to ensure project coherence and integration.
Progress Monitoring and Quality Assurance	Monitor the progress of each task, verify if the results meet expectations, and detect any emerging issues that may affect quality or deadlines.
Reporting to the Scientific Committee	Provide the SC regular reports on progress, identify technical or schedule concerns, and warn of any risks to project completion.
Contribution to EC Reporting	Deliver periodic reports with precise and up-to-date information to the EC.

Organisation of WP Meetings	Organise and execute monthly meetings with TLs, including agendas and discussions, keep the Minutes of Meeting up to date, and share other important documents.
Management of WP Communication Channels	Ensure that all members remain informed and that communication tools, such as WP mailing lists, are appropriately utilised for WP-related matters.
Participation in Review Meetings	Attend regular review meetings with the Coordination Team and Project Officer to present WP progress and address follow-up actions.

3.5.2 Task Leader

Role: The TL coordinates the execution of all planned activities carried out by the participant partners, to ensure that the aims of the task are reached without technical and temporal delays.

Task leader identification: SOLAR-MOVE project has a total of forty tasks, each led by a designated beneficiary.

The main activities and responsibilities of the TLs in the SOLAR-MOVE project are listed in Table 13.

Table 13 - SOLAR-MOVE Task Leader role

SOLAR-MOVE Task Leader roles	
Participation in WP Meetings	Attend WP meetings and give the WP Leader brief task activity reports.
Risk and Deviation Management	Assess both task risks and deviations, and report them to the WP leader and Coordination Team.
Execution of Task Activities	Manage, execute and complete all task-related activities on schedule and according with the objectives proposed.
Deliverable Preparation	Plan and prepare the respective deliverables, ensuring efforts with other task participants, and update WP leaders on the progress.

Internal Review Submission	Ensure deliverables are sent for internal revision on time and in accordance with the deliverables' guidelines set in <u>Section 5.2</u> of this document.
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3.5.3 Legal Officer

Role: the Legal Officer helps with questions involving legal requirements, regulations and documents (e.g. Consortium and GAs).

Legal Officer identification: INESC ID Legal officer (Eva Reis) and other beneficiaries' legal departments.

3.5.4 Data Protection Officer

Role: the Data Protection Officer advises on questions involving Intellectual Property Rights, open-source licences and data protection regulation.

Data protection Officer identification: INESC ID Data protection officer (Weronika Figueiredo).

4. Internal management procedures

This section presents the key tools that the SOLAR-MOVE consortium will employ to facilitate project coordination and collaboration among partners. It describes the project repository and the procedures for handling documentation (Section 4.1), details the primary methods of communication (Section 4.2), and describes the procedures for SOLAR-MOVE meetings (Section 4.3), including workflows tailored to each meeting type (Kick-off meeting and General Assemblies, SC meetings, Periodic Review meetings and WP/Task meetings).

4.1 Project Repository

Main project repository: SOLAR-MOVE workspace on Microsoft Teams and SharePoint

Content: administrative and technical documentation of the project: a range of project-related content materials, including deliverables, scientific publications and supporting resources, reports, posters, contact directories, datasets, templates, guidelines, dissemination assets, visual identity elements, presentations, Minutes of Meeting (MoMs), to name a few.

Access: strictly limited to consortium members, and invitations are only issued by the Coordinator/Project Manager, ensuring confidentiality and controlled sharing of sensitive information. When new members join the project, the beneficiary should inform the Project Manager by e-mail to grant access to the repository.

Structure: the repository is organised into WP folders, and each WP contains the respective tasks. Each task has its own folder that contains all materials resulting from the activities carried out within that task. Furthermore, there is a dedicated folder to archive all datasets used or obtained/produced during

the project. Each dataset will be accompanied by a metadata file and will be identified as Private if it is only for the exclusive use of the consortium (Figure 5).

Project Repository maintenance: responsibility of the INESC ID Coordination team. As to be detailed in the project Data Management Plan, all documentation will follow a specific nomenclature, to promote clarity and ease of access. The consortium is also committed to adhering to FAIR principles to ensure data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The Data Manager, part of the Coordination team, oversees how the repository is being used, ensures that all partners adhere to proper protocols and organisational standards, and follow the guidelines described in the SOLAR-MOVE Data Management Plan.

The screenshot displays the SOLAR-MOVE Repository interface. On the left, a sidebar shows the project logo and navigation options under 'Main Channels', including 'General' and 'Management'. The main content area features a top navigation bar with buttons for 'In library', 'In messages', '+ New', 'Upload', and 'Edit in grid view'. Below this, the 'Documents > General' section lists a series of folders: 'Datasets', 'WP1_Regulation_NTUA', 'WP2_VIPVs_iTech', 'WP3_ePIPVs_DTU', 'WP4_VIPVsDemo_Bozank', 'WP5_ePIPVsDemo_EDP', 'WP6_Business_F6S', 'WP7_Dissemination_POLIS', and 'WP8_Management_INESC'.

Figure 5 – SOLAR-MOVE Repository

4.2 Internal Communication

This section describes the communication tools and protocols established to support seamless collaboration among SOLAR-MOVE project partners:

- email correspondence and mailing lists (Section 4.2.1);
- ticketing system for requests/suggestions to the Coordinator/Project Manager (Section 4.2.2);
- virtual meetings via web calls (Section 4.2.3);
- other means of communication such as telephone calls for urgent, direct exchanges, with key decisions documented via follow-up emails; registered mail for transmitting official documents and alternative platforms like Discord for informal or supplementary communication (Section 4.2.4).

4.2.1 Email Correspondence and Mailing lists

Aim: the default mean of communication for sharing information, engaging in discussions, and distributing documents to other partners.

For all project-related correspondence, emails should clearly reference the project by including at the beginning of the subject the identifier [SOLAR-MOVE].

To improve efficiency, the partners are strongly encouraged to use the project-specific mailing lists, identified in Table 14

Table 14 - Scope of SOLAR-MOVE Email Distribution Lists

Mailing List	Email Address	Subscribers	Scope
Dissemination	solarmove.dissemination@lst.inesc-id.pt	Coordination and Communication Officer	To disseminate and provide project-related information both internally and externally.
External Expert Advisory Board	solarmove.advisory.board@inesc-id.pt	External Expert Advisory Board members	To convey strategic advice, insights and recommendations from the project's expert bodies.

Consortium	solarmove.consortium@inesc-id.pt	All contacts involved in the project	To guarantee teamwide communication and information flow.
Scientific Committee	solarmove.scientific.committee@inesc-id.pt	Scientific experts selected for the Scientific Committee	To facilitate discussions on technical topics, methodologies, and scientific approaches
WP1	solarmove.wp1@inesc-id.pt	WP1 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP1 task activities.
WP2	solarmove.wp2@inesc-id.pt	WP2 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP2 task activities
WP3	solarmove.wp3@inesc-id.pt	WP3 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP3 task activities
WP4	solarmove.wp4@inesc-id.pt	WP4 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP4 task activities

WP5	solarmove.wp5@inesc-id.pt	WP5 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP5 task activities
WP6	solarmove.wp6@inesc-id.pt	WP6 Leader and participants	To enable communication and coordination on all WP6 task activities

Moderation & management of SOLAR-MOVE mailing lists: the Coordination Team is responsible for moderating and including the contacts in the project’s mailing lists. Partners are expected to provide the contacts and specify their allocation to the different mailing lists in the Excel SOLAR-MOVE contact list shared in the *WP8_Management* folder of the project repository. All new entries should be highlighted in yellow and indicated to the Project Manager.

Email guidelines for consistency and effective communication:

- **Use of subject line identifiers:** All project-related emails subject line must begin with the tag "[SOLAR-MOVE] – Subject" to ensure messages are easily identifiable and traceable;
- **Flagging urgent matters:** Include "[ACTION REQUIRED]" or "[URGENT]" in the subject line for issues that necessitate immediate attention;
- **Document sharing:** The project's repository serves as the designated location for sharing documents. The email body should contain a direct link to the document;
- **Use of mailing lists:** Partners should communicate with one another via the mailing lists specified in Table 14, selecting the appropriate one that corresponds to the topic or Work Package;
- **Copying the Coordination Team:** The Coordinator and/or Project Manager should be copied (cc) in partner technical discussions and exchanges between partners;
- **Maintaining contact information:** Partners must update the SOLAR-MOVE Excel contact list with team contacts and mailing list assignments. The team's main contact should add the new member, place them on the proper WP mailing groups, highlight the item in yellow, and notify the Project Manager.

4.2.2 Ticket System

Ticket System: solarmove.coordination@inesc-id.pt

Aim: Partners should send requests, feedback, suggestions and inquiries to the INESC ID Coordination Team via the ticket system, to streamline support and issue tracking. With this system, when an email is submitted, a ticket is automatically created, allowing the team to efficiently monitor and manage each topic.

4.2.3 Video-Conference Calls

Main platform used: Microsoft Teams

Aim: video-conference meetings are essential for addressing technical matters, coordinating activities and efforts among the partners spread across the sixteen countries.

Type of conference meetings: meetings vary in size and purpose, including bilateral calls to resolve specific issues, SC meetings with WP leaders and Coordination team to review the progress and quality of the work, and WP meetings or Task meetings organised by WP/TL with all participant partners to advance ongoing activities. Larger meetings will also be organised, such as General Assemblies with all partners for project progress and decision making, or webinars with external stakeholders to gather feedback on the project's progress and the innovative solutions being developed.

4.2.4 Other means of internal communication

In addition to digital communication, the SOLAR-MOVE project relies on additional communication to facilitate coordination and collaboration:

- **In-person meetings:** For key events such as the Kick-off Meeting, General Assemblies, Review Meetings with the Project Officer (PO), demonstration events, and solution testing sessions, for hands-on collaboration, strategic discussion and team alignment;
- **Telephone communication:** For matters that require rapid clarification or immediate action. To ensure transparency and continuity, the outcomes of such calls should be summarised and documented, and shared with relevant participants;
- **Printed correspondence:** For formal official or legal documents, including those that require handwritten signatures (e.g., Consortium Agreement), that should be sent through registered mail, to ensure proper tracking;
- **Other communication platforms:** Partners may use additional digital platforms alongside Microsoft Teams to facilitate communication and collaboration.

4.3 SOLAR-MOVE Meetings

The SOLAR-MOVE project will host a variety of meeting formats during the length of the project to support coordination and progress tracking. Table 15 provides an overview of the recurring meeting

types along with their respective frequencies. Additional details and procedures related to each meeting category are outlined in the subsequent sections: Section 4.3.1 for General Assembly meetings, Section 4.3.2 for SC meetings, Section 4.3.3 for Periodic Review meetings, Section 4.3.4 for WP meetings.

Table 15 - SOLAR-MOVE meetings

SOLAR-MOVE Meetings	Frequency	Description / Indicative Schedule	Participants
Kick-off Meeting and General Assembly Meetings	5 On-site meetings 3 Virtual meetings	M1 (KoM) - Nov 25 – Brussels (POLIS) M6 - Apr 26 - Virtual M12 - Nov 26 – Athens (NTUA) M18 - Apr 27 - Virtual M24 - Nov 27 – Ankara (iTech) M30 - Apr 27 – Virtual M36 - Nov 28 - Copenhagen (DTU) M42 - May 29 – Portugal (INESC-ID)	- Coordination team - One representative per beneficiary
Scientific Committee meetings	42 Virtual meetings	Monthly meetings	- Coordination team - WP leaders
Periodic Review meetings	2 On-site meetings	Review Period 1: M1-21 - Brussels Review Period 2: M22-42 - Brussels	- Coordination team - WP leaders - Project Officer
Work Package meetings	Ongoing throughout each WP	Monthly, bi-weekly or weekly meetings depending on task developments.	- WP Leader - TLs -Task Participants

4.3.1 General Assembly Meetings

Aim: The General Assembly serves as the main decision-making authority of the consortium, by providing strategic guidance, authorising key project decisions, supervising financial, administrative, and governance issues, approving essential modifications, and ensuring that all partners collaborate effectively to keep the SOLAR-MOVE project aligned with its objectives, contractual commitments, and long-term vision.

Participants: Coordination and SOLAR-MOVE Beneficiaries (one representative per Beneficiary).

Frequency: In-person meetings held annually and remote meetings held in between (Table 16).

Format: in-person/hybrid and remote meetings.

Organisation: the in-person/hybrid meetings are organised by the Coordination team and host partners. The host partner is responsible for covering all associated costs, including venue rental, catering services, and the General Assembly dinner. The remote General Assembly meetings are organised by the Coordination team.

Structure: The in-person/hybrid General Assembly meeting can have a duration of one and a half days or two full days, prioritising working sessions on topics relevant for the project (e.g. working groups in specific WPs, related to the pilots). The online General Assembly meeting will last a full day, with the morning dedicated to administrative topics and the afternoon to technical updates/discussions.

The planned locations and approximate dates for upcoming General Assembly meetings are listed in Table 16.

Table 16 - SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly Meetings

SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly	Local	Host partner
M1 (KoM) – Nov 25	Brussels	POLIS
M6 – Apr 26	Virtual	Virtual
M12 – Nov 26	Athens	NTUA
M18 – Apr 27	Virtual	Virtual
M24 – Nov 27	Ankara	iTech
M30 – Apr 27	Virtual	Virtual
M36 – Nov 28	Copenhagen	DTU
M42 – May 29	Portugal	INESC-ID

Table 17 provides detailed guidelines for planning and executing General Assembly meetings.

Table 17 - SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly meetings guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly meeting guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
Coordination team sets the meeting date and prepares a draft agenda with the host partner (for on-site meetings)	3.5 months prior to the meeting
The SC reviews and validates the proposed date and agenda	3.5 months prior to the meeting
Coordination team prepares the registration form for in-person meeting.	3 months prior to the meeting
After approval, the confirmed General Assembly date and agenda are shared with the consortium and registration opens. The notice and agenda must be circulated in writing no later than 14 days before the meeting (7 days for the extraordinary meetings).	3 months prior to the meeting – no more than 14 days
For in-person General Assembly meeting, the host partner arranges logistics: venue booking, catering and networking dinner event. Venues must provide: projectors, power outlets, tables, microphones, reliable internet (for hybrid participation), enough capacity to accommodate all attendees, and easy access by public/ private transport	2 months prior to the meeting
Attendance list is shared with the consortium once registration closes.	2 months prior to the meeting
Coordination team sends to the consortium a reminder email with practical information, including link for remote access.	1 month prior to the meeting
Coordination team organises the participant presentations and finalises meeting materials (e.g. presentation templates, attendance list to sign on site)	15 days prior to the meeting
Voting procedure for decisions taken during the meeting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One vote per beneficiary - Decisions require a two-thirds (2/3) majority of the votes, with at least 2/3 of members present. - Voting may also occur via email – the coordinator circulates an email with at least 10 days for responses 	During the meeting

The meeting must be fully documented, including photographs and a hand-signed attendance sheet to ensure proper reporting and traceability.	During the meeting
Coordination Team prepares and shares the MoMs with the consortium.	Within 10 days after the meeting
Consortium should validate the MoMs. If no objections are raised within the defined period, the MoMs are considered approved.	Within 15 days of receiving the MoMs

Figure 6 illustrates the timeline and responsibilities during the General Assembly preparation.

Figure 6 – SOLAR-MOVE General Assembly meeting timeline

4.3.2 Scientific Committee Meetings

Aim: Alignment on the progress of the ongoing tasks and technical discussions, risks or management issues.

Participants: SOLAR-MOVE WP leaders and Coordination

Frequency: Once a month

Format: Remote

Organisation: Coordination team

The main guidelines for the SC meetings are described in Table 18.

Table 18 - SOLAR-MOVE Scientific Committee Meetings guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE SC meeting guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
PM schedules the SC meeting with WP leaders via Doodle	Up to 2 weeks before the meeting
PM and Project Coordinator (PC) draft the agenda PM prepares the presentation templates and sends a reminder to the meeting participants. PM asks for WP leaders to fill in the presentation template	1 week before the meeting
SC meeting is moderated by PM and PC.	During meeting
PM addresses management items. WP leaders provide updates on WP task progress, risks and delays.	During meeting
PM prepares the MoMs and sends them to the SC members via email.	Up to 1 week after the meeting
WP leaders review and validate the MoMs.	Up to 1 week after receiving the MoMs

Figure 7 represents the timeline for the organization of the SOLAR-MOVE SC meetings.

Figure 7 – SOLAR-MOVE Scientific Committee meeting time flow

4.3.3 Periodic Review Meetings

Aim: Assessment of the progress of the project and clarifications on the periodic report

Participants: SOLAR-MOVE WP leaders and Coordination

Frequency: After submission of the periodic report (expected to be at M24 and M44)

Format: In-person (generally in Brussels, last one maybe remote).

Organisation: Coordination team

The main guidelines for the Periodic Review meetings are described Table 19.

Table 19 - SOLAR-MOVE Periodic Review meeting

SOLAR-MOVE Periodic Review meeting guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
PM schedules the meeting with the Project Officer (PO) and WP Leaders and prepares the agenda. These meetings are held over 2 days: - Day 1: Pre-meeting for internal discussion and revision with WP leaders - Day 2: Review meeting with WP leaders, Coordinator and PO.	Up to 2 months prior to the meeting
PO reviews and validates the proposed agenda.	Up to 2 months prior to the meeting

PM shares the final validated agenda with all participants.	Up to 2 months prior to the meeting
Submission of the Periodic Report, prepared by Coordination Team and consortium partners, via the Funding and Tenders platform.	2 months prior to the meeting
PM prepares presentation templates and organizes participants' presentations.	1 month prior to the meeting
Day 1: Pre-meeting with Coordination and WP leaders.	Pre-meeting
Day 2: Review meeting with Coordination Team, WP leaders and PO.	Review meeting
PM prepares and sends the MoMs	Within 1 week after the meeting
Participants review and validate the MoMs.	Within 1 week after receiving the MoM
PM incorporates PO feedback, comments and required adjustments into the Periodic Report	Within 2 weeks after the meeting

Figure 8 illustrates the timeline for the SOLAR-MOVE Periodic Review meetings.

Figure 8 – Periodic Review meeting guidelines

4.3.4 Work Package Meetings

Aim: Progress of WP tasks and assessment of risks

Participants: Respective WP leader, TLs and task participants

Frequency: Monthly, bi-weekly or weekly, accordingly to the demands of each WP (intensity of workload and number of ongoing tasks)

Format: Remotely

Organisation: WP leader

The main guidelines for the WP meetings are described in Table 20.

Table 20 - SOLAR-MOVE WP meetings guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE WP meeting guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
The scheduling of the WP meetings is the responsibility of the WP leader, via a doodle poll among the WP participants (distributed via dedicated mailing list)	Up to 2 weeks prior to the meeting
The agenda is prepared and shared by the WP Leader	Up to 1 week prior to the meeting
A meeting reminder is sent by the WP leader	1 week prior to the meeting
Discussions among WP Leader and WP participants focus on tasks progress, risk assessment and next steps	During the meeting
WP leader prepares and shares the MoMs. The WP leader also places the MoMs under the respective WP Monthly meeting dedicated folder	Up to 1 week after the meetings
MoMs are validated by WP participants.	Up to 1 week after receiving the MoMs
WP leader informs the Coordination Team if WP mailing lists need to be updated. WP leaders also inform the Coordination about any reported risks/ critical delays identified during the WP meetings.	When applicable

Figure 9 illustrates the timeline for the SOLAR-MOVE WP monthly meetings.

Figure 9 – SOLAR-MOVE WP Monthly meeting

5. Quality assurance procedures

A set of procedures will be implemented to ensure effective monitoring of both progress and quality of all SOLAR-MOVE project activities and outputs. Those procedures include SOLAR-MOVE reports (Section 5.1), deliverables development, revision, and submission (Section 5.2), and the monitoring and mitigation of risks (Section 5.3).

5.1 SOLAR-MOVE Reporting

Three types of reports will be developed during the project:

- Internal Management Reports (IMRs, Section 5.1.1);
- Periodic reports to the EC (Section 5.1.2);
- Bi-monthly reports to the PO (Section 5.1.3).

The frequency of these reports and information about the respective contributors are indicated in Table 21.

Table 21 - Frequency of SOLAR-MOVE reports

SOLAR-MOVE Reports	Frequency	Contributors
Internal Management Report (IMR) <i>(*Except SONO MOTORS)</i>	Reports every 7 months covering the periods: - M1 – M7 - M8 – M14 - M15 – M21 - M22 – M28	- Coordination team - WP Leaders - TLs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M29 – M35 - M36 – M42 	
Periodic Review Reports	Two reports covering the periods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - M01 – M21 - M22 – M42 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination team - WP leaders - Tls
Bi-monthly Reports	Every two months (24 in total)	- Coordination team

*As agreed in the SOLAR-MOVE Consortium Agreement, SONO MOTORS will report the IMR to the Coordination every 3 months.

Table 22 indicates a tentative SOLAR-MOVE reporting calendar for the duration of the project and the sub-sections below describe the processes for the respective reports.

Table 22 - SOLAR-MOVE reporting calendar

SOLAR-MOVE reports	Period covered	Templates available	Deadline to send to Coordination team	Deadline to send to EU/PO
Bi-monthly report 1	Nov 2025 – Dec 2025	n/a	n/a	9/01/2026
Bi-monthly report 2	Jan 2026 – Feb 2026	n/a	n/a	06/03/2026
Bi-monthly report 3	Mar 2026 – Apr 2026	n/a	n/a	08/05/2026
IMR (M1-M7)	Nov 2025 – May 2026	M7-M8	15/05/2026	n/a
Bi-monthly report 4	May 2026 – Jun 2026	n/a	n/a	10/07/2026
Bi-monthly report 5	Jul 2026 – Aug 2026	n/a	n/a	07/09/2026
Bi-monthly report 6	Sep 2026 – Oct 2026	n/a	n/a	06/11/2026

Bi-monthly report 7	Nov 2026 – Dec 2026	n/a	n/a	08/01/2027
IMR (M8-14)	Jun 2026 – Dec 2027	M8-M14	15/05/2026	n/a
Bi-monthly report 8	Jan 2027 – Feb 2027	n/a	n/a	05/03/2027
Bi-monthly report 9	Mar 2027 – Apr 2027	n/a	n/a	07/05/2027
Bi-monthly report 10	May 2027 – Jun 2027	n/a	n/a	09/07/2027
Period Report 1 (M1-M21)	Nov 2025 – Jul 2027	M20-M21	15/08/2027	31/09/2027
Bi-monthly report 11	Jul 2027 – Aug 2027	n/a	n/a	12/09/2027
Bi-monthly report 12	Sep 2027 – Oct 2027	n/a	n/a	12/11/2027
IMR 2 (M15-21)	Jan 2028 – Feb 2028	M21-M22	15/03/2028	n/a
Bi-monthly report 13	Nov 2027 – Dec 2027	n/a	n/a	07/01/2028
Bi-monthly report 14	Jan 2028 – Feb 2028	n/a	n/a	10/03/2028
Bi-monthly report 15	Mar 2028 – Apr 2028	n/a	n/a	12/05/2028
Bi-monthly report 16	May 2028 – Jun 2028	n/a	n/a	07/07/2028
Bi-monthly report 17	Jul 2028 - Aug 2028	n/a	n/a	08/09/2028

Bi-monthly report 18	Sep 2028 - Oct 2028	n/a	n/a	05/11/2028
IMR 3 (M22-29)	Sep 2028 – Oct 2028	M35-M36	15/11/2028	n/a
Bi-monthly report 19	Nov 2028 – Dec 2028	n/a	n/a	05/01/2029
Bi-monthly report 20	Jan 2029 – Feb 2029	n/a	n/a	09/03/2029
Periodic Report 2 (M22-M42)	Aug 2027 – April 2029	M41-M42	15/05/2029	30/06/2029

5.1.1 Internal Management Reports (IMR)

Aim: Monitoring of the technical and financial progress of the project

Elaboration by: All project beneficiaries and affiliated partners, according to each IMR period and the WPs active during that reporting period.

Frequency: every 7 months (exception applies to one partner that will send the IMRs every 3 months, according to the SOLAR-MOVE CA)

Structure: The IMR consists of two documents: *i)* Management and Technical Report (Word file) and *ii)* Financial Report (Excel file)

i) The Management and Technical Report provides a comprehensive overview of the activities carried out during the reporting period, including:

- A description of the work performed by each beneficiary, detailing contributions to all relevant tasks;
- Identification of team members involved, specifying the individuals for whom effort is being reported;
- Deviations from the planned use of resources, comparing actual versus forecasted figures;
- Deviations from the work plan, such as delays in tasks or deliverables, along with justifications;
- Risks encountered, whether previously registered (see Section 5.3) or newly identified.

ii) The Financial Report details the actual effort and costs incurred by each beneficiary, including:

- Person-months reported per task and personnel costs per WP;
- Applicable expenses related to travel, consumables, and equipment;

- For equipment, beneficiaries must report the depreciated value corresponding to its use during the reporting period, in line with the agreed depreciation policy established at the project's outset.

Table 23 details the procedures and timelines for the elaboration of the IMR, also illustrated in Figure 10.

Table 23 - SOLAR-MOVE IMR guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE IMR meeting guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
Coordination team prepares and shares the IMR template (both technical and financial reports)	At least 15 days prior to the end of reporting period
Coordination sets a deadline to receive the IMRs from partners	2 weeks after the end of the reporting period
Coordination analyses all reports	Within 2 weeks after receiving the reports.
Coordination shares the results and takes mitigation actions if needed	Next SC meeting or General Assembly meeting

Figure 10 - Timeline for preparation of the SOLAR-MOVE Internal Management Report (IMR)

5.1.2 Periodic Reports to EC

Aim: EC review and assessment of the technical and financial progress of the project

Elaboration by: Coordination, all project beneficiaries and affiliated partners

Frequency: Submission at the end of P1 (M1-M21: 01-11-2025 to 31-08-2027) and P2 (M22-M42: 1-09-2027 to 30-04-2029) reporting periods.

Structure: The Periodic Report consists in a *i)* Web-based Questionnaire (to be completed directly in Sygma Platform), *ii)* Technical Report (Word file) and *iii)* Financial Report (to be completed directly in Sygma platform).

i) Web-based Questionnaire - to be completed directly on the *Sygma platform* by the INESC ID Coordination team, providing information on:

- Deliverables and milestones;
- Critical risks and mitigation strategies;
- Publications, results, and dissemination activities;
- Standards and intellectual property rights;
- Project impact and datasets;
- Composition of research teams (action directly performed by beneficiary).

ii) Technical Report

Following a template provided by the EC, the Word document will be shared in the SOLAR-MOVE project repository for all partners to complete. The technical report includes:

- Work overview and progress: A summary of project objectives, timeline, and current status of deliverables, milestones, and risk management. It also details the work performed per WP, including active tasks, achieved impact, and updates to the exploitation and dissemination plan.
- Response to previous review feedback: If applicable, this section addresses recommendations and comments from earlier evaluations.
- Open Science practices: A description of how project participants have implemented open science principles.
- Deviations from Annexes 1 and 2 from GA: This section outlines any deviations in work packages and resource usage. Beneficiaries with deviations exceeding $\pm 20\%$ from expected linear consumption, whether in personnel or direct costs, must provide a justification, including effort, cost per beneficiary, and personnel cost rates.

iii) Financial Report - to be completed by each beneficiary directly in the *Sygma portal*. Once completed, the report is validated by the Coordination team and then electronically signed and submitted by the designated Beneficiary Project Financial Signatory Person. To ensure timely submission, beneficiaries must appoint their signatory in advance. The financial report includes:

- An individual financial statement from each beneficiary, detailing the effort per WP and the use of resources across all budget categories for the reporting period;

- If “other direct costs” exceed 15% of personnel costs, beneficiaries must itemize and justify the major cost components, starting with the highest-value items. Items that collectively account for less than 15% of personnel costs may be excluded from this breakdown.

Table 24 details the periodic report workflow, also illustrated in Figure 11 (presents the Periodic Report 1; the same timeline should be followed for the subsequent Periodic Report, referring to the M22-M42 period).

Table 24 - SOLAR-MOVE Periodic report guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE Periodic report guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
The Coordination will share the template with the consortium members. This template will already have inputs from the previous IMRs and partner will have to validate and complete the information missing	Up to 15 days prior to the end of the reporting period
Coordination sets a deadline for the completion of the technical report and for completion of the financial information in the Sygma platform	2-3 weeks after the end of the reporting period
Coordination analyses all reports and requests changes by partners, if needed. In parallel, the Coordination fills in the information requested in the Sygma platform.	Within 4-6 weeks after the end of the reporting period.
Coordination submits the Periodic report in the Sygma platform	Up to 60 days after the end of the reporting period
EC reviews the Periodic report and either approves it and initiates the payment process or requests further clarifications	After submission of the periodic report
Once approved, the EC will issue a formal confirmation. After receiving this letter, the Coordination has 30 days to submit any observations, if necessary.	Within 30 days of receiving the letter
The EC proceeds with the payment transfer to the Coordinator	Within 90 days of submitting the report

Figure 11 - SOLAR-MOVE Periodic Report preparation

5.1.3 Bi-monthly reports

Aim: Regular updates to the Project Officer about the project's progress and implementation status.

Elaboration by: Coordination Team

Frequency: Every two months

Structure: Logbook-style report summarising:

- Key meetings held during the reporting period (e.g., SC meetings, work package meetings, task kick-off sessions);
- Dissemination activities carried out during the reporting period;
- Concise updates on each active task.

Table 25 details the bi-monthly report workflow, also illustrated in Figure 12.

Table 25 - SOLAR-MOVE bi-monthly report guidelines

SOLAR-MOVE bi-monthly report guidelines	
Activity/ Requirement	Timeline
The Project Manager will complete the bi-monthly meetings section with information provided on Scientific meetings, WP/Task meeting MoMs, including also dissemination and management activities that occur during the reporting period.	Until the end of the first week of the subsequent month
The Project Manager sends the bimonthly report to the PO by email	Until the end of the first week of the subsequent month

Figure 12 - SOLAR-MOVE Bi-monthly report preparation

5.1.4 Payments

The Coordination team will receive the project funding from the EC and will allocate the budget to all participating beneficiaries in accordance with the distribution plan outlined in the SOLAR-MOVE Consortium Agreement (see Table 26).

Table 26 - SOLAR-MOVE Payment Plan

Payment	Amount	Pre-condition of transfer	Notes
Pre-financing (75% of total EC contribution)	50% of the pre-financing	In the thirty (30) calendar days after receipt of pre-financing from the Granting Authority and following CA signatures and signature of the Accession Forms to the Project GA by all beneficiaries	Exception: In case a Beneficiary at any time has used 100% of the first pre-payment received from the Coordinator and can provide sufficient proof of expenses (e.g. extract from the general ledger regarding project expenses) and has submitted all due deliverables led by them up to that point, then the Coordinator will release the remaining amount of the pre-financing towards that Beneficiary.
	15% of the pre-financing	Around M10, following the approval of the 1 st Interim report.	
	10% of the pre-financing	Around M21, taking into account the requested contribution for the first period (M1-M21).	
Interim payment(s)	100%	In the ninety (90) calendar days after receipt of Interim payment(s) from the Granting Authority and once all partners provide all documents requested by project coordinator.	
Final payment	100%	Upon receipt of the payment from the Granting Authority.	

As outlined in Table 26, the payment schedule is structured as follows:

- Pre-financing: 50% of the pre-financing amount will be disbursed at the start of the project, followed by the remaining 15% after the first Internal Management Report (IMR) is approved and 10% will be made around M21;
- Interim payments: Will be made following the approval of the P1 report;
- Final payment: The balance will be transferred upon approval of the P2 report.

The INESC ID Coordination team will request bank account confirmation from all partners before proceeding with any payment transfers.

5.2 Guidelines for Creating, Reviewing, and Submitting Project Deliverables

The SOLAR-MOVE project will produce a total of 42 deliverables, as listed in

Table 4. The following sub-sections will provide guidelines for the preparation of deliverables (Section 5.2.1) and for deliverable quality control procedures (Section 5.2.2).

5.2.1 Preparation of deliverables

The following recommendations and guidelines are provided to help structure SOLAR-MOVE deliverables effectively, ensuring high-quality content and timely submission through the EC portal.

5.2.1.1 Deliverable Naming Standards

All SOLAR-MOVE deliverables must adhere to a standardized naming convention:

DX.Y_Deliverable Name.SOLARMOVE.(dd-mm-yyyy).(vx.y)

Where:

- DX.Y indicates the deliverable number
- Deliverable Name refers to the title of the document
- vx.y denotes the version number:
 - Drafts and working versions should begin at v0.1 and increment accordingly;
 - v1.0 marks the first official version submitted.

This format ensures consistency and traceability across all project documentation.

5.2.1.2 Deliverable Format Requirements

Deliverables must be prepared using the designated MS Word template or LaTeX template, available in the project repository at:

SOLAR-MOVE_General > WP7_Dissemination (POLIS) > 1. Templates > 1. Deliverables

Partners must not modify the template under any circumstances.

Before submission, the final version must be converted to *.pdf* format.

Each deliverable should be stored within its corresponding task folder, inside a dedicated subfolder for that specific deliverable. This folder should contain all working versions and supporting materials. Additionally, a separate subfolder must be created to organise files related to the revision process.

5.2.1.3 Deliverable Preparation and Recommendations

Deliverable requirements:

- Deliverables should be concise- around 30 pages;
- Content should be original, with information previously reported properly referenced;
- All deliverables should comply with the GA;
- Any technical deviations should be reported/justified during deliverable submission;
- Submission must respect the deadlines established in the GA – any delays should be immediately reported to the Coordination and consequently to the PO.
- The main types of contributors involved in the preparation of each deliverable are listed in Table 27.

Table 27 - Main participants in the SOLAR-MOVE deliverables

SOLAR-MOVE Key Roles	Description
Task Leader	Coordinates deliverable development with task participants to ensure quality and timeliness. Should notify the WP Leader and Coordination Team of schedule or technology concerns. Submits the deliverable to the reviewers and integrates the suggestions and requested changes.
Participant partners	Contribute to the preparation of the deliverable under the direction of the TL, supporting content development and review as required.
Work Package leader	Monitors deliverable progress and technical quality to meet WP goals and timelines. Notifies the Coordinator if any deviations arise.
Coordination team	Oversees the progress, informs the Project Officer of any deviations, and submits the final validated deliverable in the SYGMA portal.

The preparation process should follow the steps described in Table 28.

Table 28 - Deliverable preparation workflow

SOLAR-MOVE Key steps	Deliverable preparation workflow
Initial planning and structure development	TL (Deliverable Leader) drafts the preliminary Table of Contents (ToC)
	The tentative draft of ToC is discussed during the Task KoM.
	Partners revise the structure and define responsibilities
Ongoing development and monitoring	Regular WP/Task meetings track deliverable progress
	TL reports any delays, risks or issues to the WP leader, who then informs the Coordination team
	Coordination Team informs the PO of any technical or scheduling deviations.
Contribution and drafting process	Partners contribute directly to the document (track changes) or upload content to the designated folder.
	A complete draft should be ready 2 months (8 weeks) before the deadline
Deliverable authorship	Authorship separated by “Prepared by”: those who actively contributed to the content and writing, and “Teams involved”: those partners listed in the GA who participated, but with less significant contributions
	The first name in the deliverable authorship list should correspond to the main contribution author, followed by the authors from the same beneficiary partner placed in alphabetical order by last name
	The following beneficiaries are placed in alphabetical order. If there is more than one author per beneficiary, then the last author's name should be placed in alphabetic order.
Internal review process	WP Leader and Coordination Team receive the final draft by email for review.
	Deliverable reviewers have up to 15 working days to assess the document
Finalisation and submission	The TL includes all comments, suggestions, and modifications from the reviewers and sends the deliverable to the Coordination team at least 3 days before the EC submission deadline

	The Coordination team provides a last quality review check and may request the TL to make adjustments
	The Coordination Team submit the deliverable in the SYGMA portal, adding a brief comment detailing any technical or temporal deviation, if applicable.

5.2.1.4 SOLAR-MOVE Short version of Deliverables

To support broader visibility and dissemination, each technical SOLAR-MOVE deliverable with public dissemination level will include a concise summary of the main document, prepared by the TL. These short deliverables will provide a clear and accessible summary of the key results.

Short deliverable requirements:

- Concise summary of three pages;
- Short deliverables will not be submitted to the Sygma platform, but instead published in SOLAR-MOVE Zenodo community once the full deliverable is accepted by the PO;
- The template for short deliverables is provided at the end of the deliverable template;
- The short deliverable is prepared after sending the deliverable to the reviewers;
- The structure of the short deliverable includes an introduction outlining briefly the purpose, scope and objectives of the main document (approx. 1350-1500 characters), a methodologies and findings section describing the methods and analysing the results (approx. 4000-5400 characters) and a conclusion section summarising the main points and highlighting the significant outcomes (1350 to 1500 characters).

5.2.2 Internal Review Process for SOLAR-MOVE Deliverables

To guarantee the high quality and consistency of the SOLAR-MOVE deliverables, an internal review procedure will be applied:

- TL is expected to provide for internal revision a well-prepared document, ensuring clarity, coherent structure and consistent formatting, accurate language and style;
- Deliverables must be sent to the assigned reviewers in both Word and PDF format no later than 8 weeks before the official EC submission deadline;
- Each deliverable will be evaluated by two reviewers not involved in the task and preparation of the document;
- A guideline checklist will be provided to the reviewers to ensure consistency during the revision process;
- A list of the reviewer assignments is available on Table 29;

- If the preparation of a deliverable is delayed, the TL should immediately inform the reviewers and coordinate a new date with them;
- If a reviewer is unexpectedly unable to complete the review within the required timeframe, they should first seek an internal substitute;
- If the reviewer cannot find an internal substitute, then the Coordination team should appoint an alternative reviewer;
- Reviewers have 15 days to complete their assessment;
- Deliverables classified as “OTHER” must be submitted in the format of a short report;
- Feedback should be constructive and address the document’s structure, completeness, scientific soundness, clarity of results, coherence of conclusions, compliance with templates, quality of tables/figures, and accuracy of references;
- After receiving reviewer comments, the TL incorporates all necessary revisions and submits the final version to the Coordination Team for a last verification. This must be done at least 5 days before the EC submission deadline;
- The Coordination Team is responsible for submitting the deliverable through the Sygma platform, including a justification for any technical or temporal deviations, if applicable. Once the deliverable is submitted, the consortium is formally notified;
- After approval by the PO, deliverables will be made publicly available on the SOLAR-MOVE website. Exceptions apply to SEN-type deliverables which will be available only on the private project repository.

Table 29 - SOLAR-MOVE Deliverable reviewers

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Revision date (expected)
D1.1	Regulatory Framework Mapping	INESC ID	MOBICOM	31 Jul 2026
D1.2	Flexibility Services Mapping	INESC ID	Ustrath	30 Sep 2026
D1.3	Use Case Repository	IREC	GUNAM	31 Oct 2026
D1.4	Cybersecurity and Interoperability	EDP	DTU	31 Oct 2026
D2.1	TOPCon and SHJ Cells Prototypes	SonoM	LIST	30 Jun 2027
D2.2	PV Modules adapted to VIPVs	METU	DTU	31 Jul 2027
D2.3	MPPT Including New Algorithms	DTU	EMOT	31 Aug 2027

D2.4	V2L and V2G for VIPV Prototype	Ucant	SUSALB	31 Aug 2027
D2.5	VIPVs Prototypes	LIST	Citroen	31 Oct 2027
D2.6	Fleet Management Optimisation	EDP	INESC ID	31 Oct 2027
D2.7	PV Devices Performance Certification	INESC ID	Bonzankaya	31 Dec 2027
D3.1	PV Production in VIPVs Estimation	AA	IREC	30 Apr 2027
D3.2	Flexibility Assessment	iTech	MOBICOM	31 May 2027
D3.3	ePIPVs Planning	SonoM	ADRIA	30 Jun 2027
D3.4	ePIPVs Management and Operation	INESC TEC	Bonzankaya	31 Jul 2027
D3.5	ePIPV Hardware Solutions	Clean M	MOBICOM	31 Oct 2027
D3.6	Impact of ePIPV in Energy and Power Systems	SonoM	SUSALB	31 Dec 2027
D4.1	VIPVs Detailed Specification of VIPVs pilots	INESC ID	KAOUSSIS	30 Apr 2027
D4.2	VIPVs Pilots Installation and Commissioning	UPT	Bonzankaya	31 Oct 2027
D4.3	VIPVs Pilots Monitoring and Assessment	INESC ID	AA	31 Jul 2028
D4.4	VIPVs Lessons Learned in Pilots	INESC TEC	AA	31 Jan 2029
D5.1	ePIPVs Detailed Specification of Pilots	METU	CleanM	30 Apr 2027
D5.2	ePIPVs Pilots Installation and Commissioning	ADRIA	DTU	31 Oct 2027
D5.3	ePIPVs Pilots Monitoring and Assessment	EDP	Ucant	31 Jul 2028

D5.4	ePIPVs Lessons Learned in the Pilots	Clean M	EMOT	31 Jan 2029
D6.1	LCA of VIPV Technologies	INESC ID	ComS	31 Jan 2029
D6.2	CBA of VIPV Technologies	EDP	SonoM	28 Feb 2029
D6.3	Business Strategies and Funding Opportunities	POLIS	NTUA	30 Apr 2028
D6.4	Business Strategies and Funding Opportunities Update M42	POLIS	NTUA	30 Apr 2029
D6.5	Exploitation Methodology	GUNAM	Ustrath	31 May 2027
D7.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	DAEM	NTUA	30 Apr 2026
D7.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan Update M24	DEAM	NTUA	31 Oct 2027
D7.3	Strategy for Standardization	MOBICOM	Sonae	31 Jan 2027
D7.4	Policies and Recommendations for Procurement	Clean M	ComS	31 Oct 2028
D7.5	Regulations and Incentives Policies	F6S Tech	Sonae	31 Jan 2029
D7.6	Guidelines for VIPV and ePIPV Development	Bonzakaya	AA	30 Apr 2029
D8.1	Project Management Plan	F6S Tech	POLIS	31 Dec 2025
D8.2	Project Management Plan Update M18	F6S Tech	POLIS	30 Apr 2027
D8.3	Data Management Plan	F6S Tech	SonoM	30 Apr 2026
D8.4	Data Management Plan Update M24	iTech	INESC TEC	31 Oct 2027
D8.5	Data Management Plan Update M42	DTU	INESC TEC	30 Apr 2029

D8.6	Intermediate progress report M15	DTU	LIST	31 Jan 2027
D8.7	Intermediate progress report M36	DTU	LIST	31 Oct 2028

The deliverable preparation and internal revision process is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - SOLAR-MOVE Deliverable preparation and revision process

5.3 Risk management

Table 30 presents the critical risks identified for the SOLAR-MOVE project and the corresponding proposed mitigation strategies. Each risk is classified using a colour code that reflects its likelihood to happen and the impact on the project: low (green), Medium (yellow) and High (red).

Table 30 - Critical risks assessment for SOLAR-MOVE project

Description of risk	L ^a	S ^b	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
1. Researchers & developers leave the team.	High	High	All	Teams are very versatile, so existing collaborators can be quickly assigned to the project and highly qualified workforce replace leaving researchers.
2. Integration with HV systems of the Trucks.	Medium	High	WP2	The connection with HV system in trucks is complex mainly in the Heavy Duty and passenger bus. If the connection to HV is not possible, the partners will use LV system.
3. Difficulty of finding and using appropriate free solvers in complex optimisation problems.	Medium	High	WP3	Free solvers are usually very restricted in terms of solving large and complex problems. Thus, commercial solvers can be used to solve complex problems, such as mixed integer nonlinear problems, offer greater accuracy. Also, partners like INESC, DTU, and METU have strong expertise in the development/implementation of solvers and optimisation algorithms.

4. Issues in the integration of the algorithms with legacy systems already in place.	Medium	Medium	WP3	Partners such as Mobicom and ComS have strong experience in development and integration of algorithms in platforms. Effective communication and continuous effort from the early stages of the project are essential for standardising inputs and outputs to integrate all tools.
5. Time spent for economic and technical coordination between partners.	Medium	Medium	WP1- WP7	INESC ID possesses strong expertise in project management. To mitigate delays and communication issues between partners, a strategy will be implemented to establish regular meetings at the consortium level (G.A.), with WP leaders (SC), and with TLs (organised by WP leaders).
6. Markets and VIPVs related regulation impacting the SOLARMOVE solutions	Medium	Medium	WP2 WP3 WP6 WP7	Partners are aware of the most innovative ideas and trends. However, regulation analysis and the ongoing initiatives will be identified in WP1. Additionally, in WP7, SOLARMOVE partners will develop a comprehensive policy recommendation and strategic positioning framework.
7. Inconsistency between tools, models and methods developed by the partners.	Low	Medium	WP2 WP3	Close collaboration between involved partners from the early stages of the project to clearly define the interfaces of the tools and models.
8. Delay in the development of tools and models due to the underestimation of technical complexity and resources.	Medium	High	WP2 WP3 WP4	Continuous monitoring of progress will be implemented, with additional project resources allocated if deviations or unexpected delays arise. Furthermore, the algorithms will be developed in modules, following an agile methodology with sprints. As a result, delays in the development of any individual module will have minimal impact on the overall project execution.
9. Difficulties to assure interoperability between proposed solutions and external systems (SOs).	Low	Medium	WP3 WP5	WP1 will include a task for the definition of cybersecurity, interoperability, and integration requirements, which will be considered in the developments in of ePVIV solutions mainly in WP3.

10. Technical mistakes in assembling of equipment at demo sites.	Low	Medium	WP4 WP5	The duration of tasks related to the pilots was planned to accommodate unexpected issues during the testing phase. Partners will develop and cross-check a detailed installation diagram before commencing the process.
11. Obstacles (grid connection and space limits, permits) in deploying PV modules at demonstrators.	Low	Medium	WP5	The conditions for connecting additional panels will be investigated in Phase 1. If there are indications that solutions cannot be applied, alternative methods will be tried, or other demonstrators will be used. In the worst case, the efficiency measurements will be done in an off-grid manner, and results will be projected.

Throughout the project, unexpected risks may arise, such as sudden increases in costs for materials, personnel, or travel due to inflation. It is the responsibility of all partners to identify and report these risks at both the task and work package levels. Reports should be communicated first to the respective TL, who escalates them to the WP Leader, and ultimately to the Coordination Team and the Scientific Committee/General Assembly.

Risk identification can be informed by monitoring deliverables' progress, WP achievements, milestone completion, and insights from IMRs and Periodic reports. Risk monitoring is conducted monthly during SC meetings, every seven months in IMRs, annually in General Assemblies, and in periodic reports.

If a risk materialises, the project will implement proactive mitigation measures to limit its impact. These may include reallocating resources, revising timelines, or enhancing communication and coordination among partners (see Table 30).

6. Communication and Dissemination Preliminary plan

Aim: comprehensive set of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities aimed at maximizing the project's impact and visibility. These activities are guided by the Communication and Dissemination Plan, first delivered as D7.1 at month 6 and updated as Deliverable D7.2 at M24.

Responsible: POLIS

The SOLAR-MOVE consortium will develop a set of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities outlined in WP7, led by POLIS, to ensure the maximisation of the project impact. An initial plan has been agreed in the GA and will be detailed and adjusted in the D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

As part of the initial plan, the dissemination and communication activities, will engage key stakeholders (Table 31) across all project phases to achieve the following objectives: i) increase awareness of the project's vision and goals; ii) disseminate the research, scientific, and technological knowledge

produced by SOLAR-MOVE, including its innovations, and communicate their benefits to target audiences; iii) maximise knowledge and innovation transfer; iv) identify suitable market segments to support the exploitation strategy; v) inform regulatory bodies and propose regulatory modifications; and vi) promote collaboration and synergy with other projects and initiatives.

Table 31 - Target Groups (TG) of the SOLAR-MOVE expected results (Figure 2.1 from GA)

Target Groups	Description
End Users	TG1 EV drivers/owners and families, vehicle operators.
	TG2 Garbage Trucks + Commercial fleet managers.
	TG3 Bus fleet managers.
	TG4 Post company (transportation), logistics and distribution fleet managers.
	TG5 Retailers (e.g. SONAE).
	TG6 Last-Mile delivery fleet managers.
	TG7 Motorhome drivers/travellers and fleet managers.
Stakeholder ecosystem	TG8 PV cell manufactures and PV integrators.
	TG9 Vehicle manufactures; Fleet operators; Battery manufactures, OEMs, and electronic equipment manufacturers.
	TG10 Energy industry: System operators (DSO, TSO), energy producers, energy retailers and aggregators, energy service companies, VPP, and CPO.
	TG11 Research and Academia: Scientific Community, R&D, Students, Programme projects/joint actions, and European open science cloud.
	TG12 Technology providers: software companies, hardware devise, IoT services, building operators, weather services, and cybersecurity solutions.
	TG13 Standardisation Bodies: BRIDGE, IEC, CIRED, ISO, and IEA.
	TG14 Policymakers, Public Authorities and Regulators: EU commission, European parliament, city mayors, and members states heads.

SOLAR-MOVE project will deliver significant value to VIPVs and eIPVs end users (TG1-TG7). Dissemination and communication initiatives will be designed to engage and enlighten present and future VIPVs and eIPV end users for optimum impact and communication. SOLAR-MOVE D&C will also promote collaboration and VIPV and eIPV development and adoption among ecosystem stakeholders (TG8-TG14). This set of stakeholders will participate in project Advisory Board activities including webinars and events. Stakeholder groups will offer vital insights, input on SOLAR-MOVE methodology, solutions, and innovations, regulatory regulations, and market expectations to maximise the project's exploitation potential.

For successful end-user engagement and VIPVs and eIPVs adoption, D&C activities will be developed at two levels: i) Local/national-targeted communication to Denmark, Greece, Turkey, Albania, Portugal, and Slovenia, where SOLAR-MOVE pilots will be conducted. The project's English materials will be translated into the local language and made available on the project website and social media, distributed at local events and conferences, and shared directly with target groups to maximise its impact on local VIPVs and eIPV end users; and ii) European/International-targeted communication, directed to European institutions and worldwide countries and global energy markets, to promote knowledge. Note that New Zealand is part of the partnership, ensuring solutions are applicable across regulatory environments. SOLAR-MOVE partners will attend worldwide conferences and fairs and publish in peer-reviewed international journals and specialist periodicals. Figure 14 shows the project's main dissemination initiatives.

Figure 14 - Main Dissemination activities of the SOLAR-MOVE project (Figure 2.2 from GA)

To assess the project's dissemination impact, the SOLAR-MOVE consortium will use indicators from Table 32 and Table 33.

Table 32 - Impact of the SOLAR-MOVE project's dissemination activities (Table 2.3 from GA)

KPI	Targets	Dissemination activities aim	TGs	Tools and channels
No. of workshops organised	3	Co-design workshop addressing usability and aesthetic factors in VIPV solutions.	TG1-TG7	Project presentation, poster brochure, leaflets.
No. of attendees to the project workshops	40			
Clarification sessions	5	Enhancing end users' awareness and understanding of SOLAR-MOVE solutions.	TG1-TG7	Project presentation, brochures, leaflets
No. of demo events	4	Dissemination of results to target groups, identification of cooperation opportunities, and increased awareness and engagement of end users.	All	Project presentation, brochure, leaflets, social media, media news, website.
Webinars	5	Increase awareness on VIPVs and ePIPVs and SOLAR-MOVE solutions and external monitoring of the project, organised every 6 months, starting at M9.	ALL	Brochure, leaflets, poster, roll-up, website.
Attendance in events	20	Dissemination and exchange during conferences, networking events, and industry fairs attracting energy system stakeholders.	TG8-TG14	Brochure, leaflets,
No. of events where the project has been presented	5		TG8-TG14	Project presentation, roll-up, poster.
No. of articles in specialised magazines	2	Share the detailed knowledge created in the project to allow industry to improve and create new solutions, and policymakers to follow.	TG8, TG9, TG10, TG12	Industry press, media, conferences.
No. of scientific publications	25	Share the detailed knowledge created in the project to allow other researchers to build upon the findings of the project.	TG10, TG11, TG12	Conferences, scientific press, media.
No. of PhD/MSc thesis	6	Training of early-stage researchers and dissemination of the project results.	TG10, TG11, TG12	Project website and social channels.
Liaisons and joint activities with other projects, communities, initiatives.	12	Ideas gathering, knowledge, and best practice exchange with similar initiatives. Joint events, publications.	TG10, TG11, TG12	Website, joint publications, social media, workshops.
Guidelines on VIPVs and ePIPVs	3	To promote VIPVs and ePIPVs adoption among end users and ensure the project's long-term impact.	ALL	Website, social channels, news.
No. of scientific/technical dissemination material	3	Communication of SOLAR-MOVE results and achievements.	All TGs	Website, brochure, leaflets, poster.

Table 33 - SOLAR-MOVE project's communication tools and channels, and KPIs (Table 2.4 from GA)

Channel	KPI	Targets	Expected Impact	TG
SOLAR-MOVE Website	No. of unique visitors	2 000	Main online information channel; Liaisons with other initiatives, projects, and WG; Communication of project news, events, and outcomes; Increase awareness and engagement with the project.	All TGs
	Average duration of visits	2 min		
	No. of page views	5 000		
	Deliverable downloads	300		
Project second social media	No. of accumulative followers	200	Increased visibility and interest of TGs (Fig. 2.1) and citizens; Direct communication with followers, engagement with the project.	All TGs
	No. of posts (at least 1 per week)	168		
Project LinkedIn	No. of accumulative followers	500	Increased project visibility and impact on society.	All TGs
	No. of posts (at least 1 per week)	168		
Publications in general media	No. of articles in magazines, newspapers	20		All TGs
Outreach events	Participation in events such as European Research Night	3	Enhance end users' awareness of EU projects and VIPVs and ePIPVs.	TG1-TG7
Branding and communication kit	No. of press releases (2); factsheets/brochures (2); presentations (1); posters (4); banners (1); eNewsletters (14, every 3 months); videos (1)		Communication of project news, events, and results; Increased awareness; Unique branding and visual identity of the project.	All TGs

7. Evidence and record-keeping

Aim: this section outlines the procedures and requirements for the retention of evidence, record keeping, and archiving of project documents and results within SOLAR-MOVE. These measures guarantee complete adherence to Horizon Europe requirements concerning audits, reviews, checks, and controls, emphasising the public character of EU funding and the European Commission's obligation to verify the proper utilisation and impact of the financed activities.

All European Union-funded projects are required to maintain evidence supporting the project activities and financial expenditures. Beneficiaries must be able to demonstrate compliance with the GA and Horizon Europe rules at any point during the project lifecycle and after its completion. Failure to provide adequate and timely evidence may result in the rejection of declared costs or the recovery of funds already paid. Therefore, maintaining complete, organised, and accessible records is crucial to ensure transparent, efficient, and compliant project management. First, all the documentation necessary is numbered in the Section 7.1 , followed by the information regarding the archive methods (Section 7.2) and responsibilities and access rights (Section 7.3), retention period (Section 7.4) and verification and compliance (Section 7.5).

7.1 Scope of Archived Documentation

Partners must archive documentation covering, at a minimum, the following categories:

7.1.1 Financial Records

- Detailed accounting records related to project costs;
- Personnel contracts and employment documentation;
- Signed and dated timesheets or time declarations, where applicable;
- Proofs of payment (e.g. bank statements, payment confirmations);
- Invoices and supporting expenditure documentation;
- Financial reports and cost justifications linked to technical activities.

Special attention must be given to **personnel costs**, for which accurate and complete time records are mandatory. Costs not supported by adequate evidence may be considered ineligible.

7.1.2 Technical Records

- Description of Action (DoA);
- Project deliverables and milestone reports;
- Technical and scientific reports;

- Documentation supporting task implementation and progress;
- Evidence demonstrating the achievement of project results.

7.1.3 Legal, Management, and Ethics Records

- GA and any amendments;
- Consortium Agreement;
- Subcontracting and third-party agreements;
- Ethics approvals and GDPR-related documentation;
- Minutes of meetings, decision records, and internal procedures.

Beneficiaries are also responsible for ensuring that their affiliated entities comply with the same documentation and archiving obligations.

7.2 Archiving Repositories and Methods

Project documentation should be archived using secure and reliable systems that ensure data integrity, traceability, and long-term accessibility:

- **Digital repositories:** institutional and project-designated shared repositories with controlled access, versioning mechanisms, and regular backups;
- **Physical archives:** secure storage for signed originals where required by law or contractual obligations.

All archiving procedures must guarantee that documents remain readable, accessible, and usable throughout the retention period.

7.3 Responsibilities and Access Rights

- Each beneficiary is responsible for archiving its own financial, technical, and administrative documentation related to SOLAR-MOVE.
- The Project Coordinator ensures overall consistency at project level and facilitates availability of documentation when required.
- Access to archived material is restricted to authorised personnel. EU institutions and other authorised bodies may request access to documentation in the context of audits, reviews, or checks.

7.4 Retention Period

All project documents and results must be retained for a minimum period of five (5) years after the payment of the balance, or longer if required by national law or in the case of ongoing audits, reviews, or investigations.

Mandatory audits apply to beneficiaries declaring actual costs exceeding EUR 400,000, but all beneficiaries remain subject to audit and verification procedures regardless of budget size.

7.5 Verification and Compliance

Compliance with these requirements will be verified through the availability and completeness of archived documentation upon request by the European Commission or authorised bodies.

Each partner may, if requested, provide a short declaration confirming that they have:

- Archived all required financial, technical, and administrative records;
- Stored documentation in secure, controlled-access repositories;
- Implemented version control and backup procedures;
- Ensured availability of records for audits, reviews, or checks.

8. Conclusions

The Project Management Plan provides a comprehensive framework for the coordination and governance of the SOLAR-MOVE project, outlining the collaboration tools, internal procedures, and quality assurance mechanisms necessary to guarantee effective execution. It establishes the basis for systematic project implementation, facilitates effective communication among all partners, and ensures the prompt achievement of activities and milestones. This deliverable delineates the management and governance framework of SOLAR-MOVE and specifies the operational procedures to be implemented by the consortium. As the initial management deliverable, D8.1 is instrumental in establishing a well-organised and cohesive management framework, underpinning the project's overarching goal to develop and showcase innovative VIPV and eIPV solutions that can be broadly implemented across various contexts.

9. References

[1] SOLAR-MOVE, Consortium Agreement, version 9 dated 12/09/2025, DESCA Consortium Agreement Model (SOLAR-MOVE internal document). Available: [Grant Agreement - GAP-101235635.pdf](#) Accessed: 21-11-2025

[2] Periodic Reports, Horizon 2020 Online Manual. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/reports/periodic-reports_en.htm. Accessed: 21-11-2025

ANNEX I

SOLAR-MOVE Project Repository

Access to the Project Repository

The SOLAR-MOVE Microsoft Teams repository is accessible through a web browser without the need for any specialised software and is restricted to Project Partners. To access the repository:

- Partners are required to request access by contacting the SOLAR-MOVE Coordination/Project Manager through the designated mailing list.
- Once access is granted by the Coordination, partners will receive an email notification with a secure link to the repository. Partners may access the repository by either generating new or using existing Microsoft credentials. Occasionally, to prevent conflicts with existing Teams accounts, it is advisable to open the link using an Incognito Window.
- If partners encounter difficulties accessing the repository, they should contact the SOLAR-MOVE Coordination team for support.

Utilising the Repository

The SOLAR-MOVE General folder contains the following folders:

- WP1_Regulation, Services and Use Cases (NTUA) – contains Task 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;
- WP2_VIPVs Innovation and Development (iTech) - contains Task 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;
- WP3_Planning and Operation of ePIPVs (DTU) - contains Task 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;
- WP4_VIPVs Demonstration (Bonzakaya) - contains Task 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;
- WP5_ePIPVs in cities and building (EDP NEW) - contains Task 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;
- WP6_Business Models and Funding Opportunities (F6STech) - contains Task 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 folders. Each Task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL;

- WP7_Dissemination and Standardization (POLIS) – contains Task 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4 and 7.6 folders. Each task folder will contain all information regarding the developed activities, deliverables, scientific articles. Each task folder is managed by the TL. Task 7.1 includes subfolders designated for the project’s visual identify project, SOLAR-MOVE logos, partners logos, an Event folder to encompass all upcoming project-related events, a Scientific articles folder containing all conference and journal scientific articles, Media activities folder with all the activities in social media and website, templates folder comprising all project template documents, including deliverable, MoMs, PPT, Attendance list templates;
- WP8_Project Management (INESC ID) – Subfolders include: Proposal (with all the information exchanged during proposal phase), Consortium Agreement and GA folder (with all the legal documents of the project), Meeting folder (with all the information about Project meetings including SC meetings, General Assembly meetings, Review meetings), Deliverables (with Management deliverables, and guidelines for the development and revision of deliverables), and a SOLAR-MOVE contact mailing list;
- Datasets – all datasets used/created within the project, accompanied by metadata files (each dataset organized in a dedicated folder).

Uploading and downloading files from the repository

Partners can upload documents to the repository using either of the following methods:

- Navigate to the desired folder and select “Upload file”.
- Drag and drop the file directly into the folder.

To download files or folders:

- click the "More options" (three dots) icon in front of the file/folder,
- Select "Download."

Additional options include adding to favourites, viewing details, accessing previous versions, moving, copying, or deleting the item.

Editing Files

Microsoft Teams enables real-time multiple, collaborative editing. To edit a file:

- Open the file directly from the Teams repository.
- Make your edits in review mode; ensuring changes are tracked.

All modifications are automatically saved and visible to all users with access.

Version Control

Microsoft Teams tracks document changes and maintains version history. To view or restore previous versions:

- click the "Open in SharePoint" via three dots in front of the file;

- Select “Version history” option (three dots) where earlier versions can be reviewed or restored as needed.

The platforms’ integrated collaboration and version-tracking features ensure partners always work on the most up-to-date document, while a full record of changes is maintained for transparency and quality assurance.

Syncing files with the computer

To synchronise the SharePoint files and folders with your computer, open the SOLAR-MOVE project SharePoint, navigate to the Documents page, and click on the three dots (synchronisation button).